

New technologies and medias

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

Do you have at least one television at home? Oui
 Non

How many screens (computers, tablets, mobile phones) do you have at home? None
 1 to 2
 3 to 4
 5 to 6
 More than 6

How many games consoles do you use at home? 0
 1
 2
 3
 More than 3

How many of these screens and consoles are connected to the Internet? 0
 1 to 2
 3 to 4
 5 to 6
 More than 6

Do you have a mobile phone? Oui
 Non

Is this mobile phone yours or do you share it ? It is mine
 I share it with someone else

How much time per day do you spend watching television during the school week? I don't watch TV
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours
(Outside school)

How much time per day do you spend watching television during the weekend? I don't watch TV
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours

How much time per day do you listen to the radio during the school week? I don't listen to the radio
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours
(Outside school)

How much time per day do you listen to the radio during the weekend?

- I don't listen to the radio
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours

How long are you on the computer and tablet per day, during the school week?

- I don't use a computer or a tablet
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours
 (Outside school)

Who decides how much time you spend in front of the computer and tablet during the school week ?

- No one, I decide for myself.
 My parents or guardian or adult I live with.

How long are you on the computer and tablet per day, during the weekend ?

- I don't use a computer or a tablet
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours

Who decides how much time you spend in front of the computer and tablet during the weekend ?

- No one, I decide for myself.
 My parents or guardian or adult I live with.

How long are you on your mobile phone per day during the school week?

- I don't use a mobile phone
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours
 (Outside school)

Who decides how much time you spend on your mobile phone during the school week?

- No one, I decide for myself.
 My parents or guardian or adult I live with.

How long are you on your mobile phone per day during the weekend?

- I don't use a mobile phone
 Less than 1 hour
 Between 1 and 2 hours
 Between 2 and 3 hours
 Between 3 and 4 hours
 Between 4 and 5 hours
 More than 5 hours

Who decides how much time you spend on your mobile phone during the weekend?

- No one, I decide for myself.
 My parents or guardian or adult I live with.

At what time of day do you spend the most time in front of the screens at the weekend?

- Morning
 Afternoon
 Evening
 Throughout the day, when I want to

Where do you use your computer or tablet most ?

- Bedroom
- Kitchen
- Living room
- Outdoor space (terrace, garden, balcony,)
- Other

Where do you use your smartphone most ?

- Bedroom
- Kitchen
- Living room
- Outdoor space (terrace, garden, balcony,)
- Other

How much time per day do you spend playing video games during the school week?

- I don't play video games
- Less than 1 hour
- Between 1 and 2 hours
- Between 2 and 3 hours
- Between 3 and 4 hours
- Between 4 and 5 hours
- More than 5 hours
(Outside school)

Who decides how much time you spend playing video games during the school week?

- No one, I decide for myself.
- My parents or guardian or adult I live with.

How much time per day do you spend playing video games during the weekend?

- I don't play video games
- Less than 1 hour
- Between 1 and 2 hours
- Between 2 and 3 hours
- Between 3 and 4 hours
- Between 4 and 5 hours
- More than 5 hours

Who decides how much time you spend playing video games during the weekend?

- No one, I decide for myself.
- My parents or guardian or adult I live with.

Do your family encourage you to reduce your screen time?

- Oui
- Non

Which parent?

- Father
- Mother
- Other family member

How often do they encourage you?

- Rarely
- From time to time
- Very frequently

When you are on the computer and/or tablet, what type of actions do you most often perform?

- Searching for general information
- Discussion by email or on the digital social networks with friends or family
- Watching your social network feed
- Listening to the music
- Playing games
- Study or homeworks
- Viewing videos
- Other

When you are on your mobile phone, what type of actions do you perform most often?

- Searching for general information
- Discussion by email or on the digital social networks with friends or family
- Watching your social network feed
- Listening to the music
- Playing games
- Study or homeworks
- Viewing videos
- Telephone conversation
- Other

On which platforms do you watch videos?

- Youtube
- Tik-tok
- Facebook
- Instagram
- Snapchat
- On streaming websites
- Other

Do you watch videos from a specific or particular youtuber, tik-toker, instagramer... ?

- Yes, I have favorites I like to watch regularly
- No, I don't follow anyone
- Yes, I have favorites that I watch and I also watch others that come up

Which one do you follow?

Have you ever felt like buying food products by watching some youtubers, tik-tokers, instagramers...?

- Oui
- Non

Which ones?

Did you buy them?

- Oui
- Non